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SMART ENERGY-EFFICIENT BUILDINGS FOR SMART ENERGY GRIDS AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Abstract

This article examines the use of smart technologies in buildings and whether the use of smart technologies affects the performance of the circular economy of buildings in terms of energy and water consumption, their marginal cost, and the time and quality of management decisions for building management companies.

To address these strategic issues, the construction model must evolve towards a new interdisciplinary approach that will expand the scope and impact of future developments, improving collaboration with ICT, energy and other sectors.

In the study, a computer model was developed to simulate the processes of heat and mass transfer in the building and in each structural element and the relationships between the elements. The results of the study suggest that the introduction of smart technologies to create a smart infrastructure is useful for the operation of buildings in a circular economy.

The results of the study proved that the impact of smart technologies on the efficiency of buildings in the circular economy is positive, as it reduces the cost of utilities and reduces the time required for management decisions. The results show that investing in smart technologies in buildings is of significant value and will improve the circular economy performance of buildings in terms of low energy and water use, and effective management decisions.

This article can form the basis for a project proposal aimed at developing and building a network management infrastructure for an intelligent grid that allows the use of intelligent distributed applications and control devices that provide maximum reliability, survivability and speed.

Keywords: smart energy-efficient buildings, smart energy grids, circular economy, building information models, smart home software services.

Electricity distribution grids have traditionally been centrally controlled at a large scale. However, in the future smart grids there will be a growing need for more active participation in the power systems on the part of consumers as well as increasing concern about environment and energy efficiency issues.

According to the European Union Directive on the Energy Performance of Buildings (EPBD 2002/91/EC), more than 40% of the energy consumption in Europe is due to heating, cooling and lighting operations within buildings. Moreover, buildings are the largest source of CO₂ emissions in the EU (including their electric power consumption), and their total energy has been rising since 1990.

The targets on energy efficiency can only be achieved with the contribution from many different sources, coming from all energy system stakeholders, customers, utilities, manufacturers, industries, governmental actors and regulators.

One of the most important contributions comes from the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) sector and Circular Economy (CE).

Buildings components (cement, steel, insulation, glass windows) and systems (lighting, heating, ventilation and air conditioning appliances) are developed by independent companies

whose products are tested for individual performance independently of each other. While this must be encouraged and is necessary, it is insufficient. A whole building approach to the design and operation of buildings, where these components are integrated in a way that they reduce consumption through cooperation, is rarely used. This often leads to significant system-level inefficiencies [1].

The ICT sector can deliver simulation, modeling, analysis, monitoring and visualization tools that are vitally needed to facilitate a whole building approach to both the design and operation of buildings.

The ICT have an important role to play in reducing the energy intensity and therefore increasing the energy efficiency of the economy.

Note: the energy intensity is a measure of energy efficiency of a national economy:
 $EI = \text{Energy units}/\text{GDP} = \text{MJ}/\$$

As ICT is today pervasive to all industrial and business domains, it is expected to generate a deep impact in the energy efficiency of the buildings of tomorrow (should they be new or renovated).

The mentioned document focuses on ICT as a support to energy efficiency in co-called smart buildings. Moreover, the focus is on the building itself, including equipments and devices, the envelope and the potential connections with the outside (e.g. electric grids).

It is clear that, if Europe is to succeed and achieve its ambitious objectives, the role of ICT as enabler of energy efficiency across the economy needs to be fully explored and exploited.

In order to put ICT at the core of the energy efficiency effort and to enable them to reach their full potential, it is necessary to foster research into novel ICT-based solutions and strengthen their take-up – so that the energy intensity of the economy can be further reduced by adding intelligence components, equipment and services. Therefore, it is essential to reinforce multidisciplinary RTD involving researched from the ICT, the energy and building domains, to foster the use of national, international and regional programmes for the deployment of ICT-enabled research results (like large-scale pilots of energy management systems for public and commercial building, and to support awareness raising and foster exchanges of information involving these issues [2].

The cross-fertilization of buildings and ICT has to deal with the key following expectations:

1. The generalization of “Energy-positive Smart Buildings”. Energy-positive buildings are transforming buildings from pure consumers to “prosumers” (producers and consumers). Smart buildings means buildings empowered by ICT in the context of the merging Ubiquitous Computing and the Internet of Things: the generalization in instrumenting buildings with sensors, actuators, micro-chips, micro- and nano-embedded systems will allow to collect, filter and produce more information locally, to be further consolidated and manages globally according to business functions and services.

2. Relaying to item 1, buildings will play a new and key role in innovative distributed energy production and new associated business models for renewable energy management, storage and peak shaving: they are to move from “end of pipe” buildings to active nodes in smart grids. They will permit to optimize the local distributed production and storage of energy/electricity, to deal with shaving consumption peaks and the optimization of energy consumption, to deal with the management of some local coordination of the energy system, while at the same time ensuring appropriate integration with smart energy grids – including securing the provision at any time of the energy (where ever it comes from local or global), all this in a systems approach and according to some various contexts (user profiling, security level, etc.).

3. The development of interoperable business applications and services (like BIMs – Building Information Models) to deal with enhanced diagnostic and renovation of existing buildings and infrastructures and simulations to access variants of environmental performance of buildings, tools for dynamic building evaluation at run-time, and allowing optimization based on multi-dimensions / multi-criteria constraints, etc.

4. The required need to deal with the increasing volume and complexity of all the information generated by the systems mentioned in the previous items, potentially coupled whenever required with the huge mass of information over the Internet, and also to deal with knowledge that is already available but not easily accessible: tools already exist in this area or are currently emerging, but still need developments and have to be apprehended by Construction stakeholders to fully take benefits of the advances in this area, e.g. thanks to large-scale pilots and demonstrations.

5. Construction stakeholders and user's awareness, to be achieved through innovative, pervasive and friendly user interfaces and CE. User awareness is a key factor for moving to eco-friendly behavior. However, very few building-owners know what consumes the most energy in their building(s) and even fewer look regularly and accurately at the energy meter attached to their building since it remains an uneasy and tedious task. There is a need for new user interfaces/energy-displays that will provide attractive content at the appropriate time, through a motivational approach and with intuitive and smart design.

In order to address these strategic topics, the construction model must evolve towards a new multidisciplinary approach which will empower the scope and impact of future developments, improving cooperation with ICT, energy and other sectors.

As example of such multidisciplinary approach one can describe some cooperative projects between Belarus and Germany (A.V.Luikov Heat and Mass Transfer Institute, Belarus, and the University of Stuttgart, Germany).

During the cooperation a computer model for simulation of heat and mass transfer processes in building and in each constructive element and relationships among elements was developed.

Method of the calculation based on the building energy balance [4] is the following:

Governing equation takes in to account:

Heat losses through walls and roof;

Thermal resistance of the walls and roofs may be different;

Ventilation heat losses;

Improvement of the walls insulation;

Daily regulation of the heat consumption.

Governing energy balance equation

$$V \cdot \rho \cdot C_p \frac{dT}{d\tau} = -K(T - T_{out}) - G_v C_p (T - T_{out}) + Q \quad (1)$$

where

$$K = \sum k_i A_i \quad (2)$$

$$k_i = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{\alpha_i^{in}} + \sum \frac{\delta_k}{\lambda_k} + \frac{1}{\alpha_i^{out}}} \quad (3)$$

α_i^{in} - internal heat transfer coefficient;

α_i^{out} - external heat transfer coefficient;

δ_k - thickness of the walls or insulation;

G_v - mass ventilation rate;

Q - energy sources;

k_i - total heat transfer coefficient;

A_i - wall surface;

λ_k - coefficient of thermal conductivity of the wall material;

C_p - air thermal conductivity.

Governing equation for natural convection calculations based on theoretical and experimental considerations can be written as follow:

$$A G_v^2 = g * (\rho_{out} - \rho_{in}) (4)$$

where

ρ_{out}, ρ_{in} - external and internal air density; $g = 9.81 \text{ m/c}^2$.

Coefficient A depends on building design and can be considered as a constant for the similar building types. This equation allows getting correlation factor for taking in to account variation of the outside temperature. It looks like:

$$g_v = g_{vn} \sqrt{\frac{t_{in} - t_{out}}{t_{in} - t_{out}^n}} (5)$$

where

g_{vn} - mass ventilation rate for standard outside and inside temperatures;

t_{out}^n - outside temperature for which the rated mass ventilation rate is calculated.

Any building can be approximated as a composition of rectangular elements, which can be described by the set of parameters:

- Wall materials, which can be defined by heat conductivity coefficients,
- Geometrical characteristics like walls, windows or doors height, width, length and thickness,
- Heat sources inside elements,
- Standard requirements for ventilation, which use to define how much times the air inside elements has to be refreshed during the 24 hours.

Any rectangular element of the set has six walls and can be associated with relevant number of element and the numbers of walls. As far the building is approximated by composition of elements the relation between the elements can be established by conferring the mutual walls of elements the coincided numbers.

Fig.1 Diagram for calculation of energy balance of building's element

Thus, to construct the model for calculation of energy balance of total building, which consists of separate elements like shown in the Figure 1 it is enough to numerate the facets of elements that, the mutual facets had the same numbers. The results of numbering of the elements facets can be summarized as matrix $W(N, 6)$ that contains the facets numbers of elements, being had the same numbers of the mutual facets of elements. The row number of the matrix $W(N, 6)$ corresponds to number of element and every row contains facets numbers. Obviously, the repeating numbers are associated with internal walls of the building. Matrix $W(N, 6)$ can be used for construction of vector $B(M)$, which components contain numbers of outside facets. Next step is definition of vector $K(P)$ for keeping of values of heat transfer coefficients for all facets. The components of vector $K(P)$ are to be defined with taking into account that mutual facets of the elements have the same heat transfer coefficients. These coefficients must be calculated by using equation (3) with taking into account of all features of the facets (windows, doors and etc).

The mention above matrix and vectors allow calculating all indexes for coefficients of the energy balance equations set for calculation of temperature for each elements of the model of building.

For $E=1, N$

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^6 K(W(E,i)) + \rho * G_v(E) * C_p \right) * T(E) - \sum_{i=1}^q K(W(E,i)) * T(p_i) =$$

$$= Q_E + G_v * C_p * T_{out} + \sum_{i=1}^r K(B(i)) T_{out} \quad (6)$$

In the equations set (6) Indexes P_i are associated with internal elements numbers to be connected to element E and q is an amount of the elements. This index can be calculated by using the matrix $W(N, 6)$. Indexes $B(i)$ are associated with numbers of outside facets of element E and included all numbers, which meets the requirements:

$$B(i) \in W(E, 6) \quad (7)$$

The results of solution of equation set (6) are the temperature of all elements of the building to be modeled.

The Object Oriented Programming (OOP) [5] was used to develop basic framework of computerized model of heat and mass transfer processes in buildings. The main advantage of the OOP is the possibility to develop a model with huge data arrays in various formats while decoupling different technological processes in the model structure. Using this modeling technique makes it possible to model the various processes used in a production or economic system, or human society while maintaining transparency and user-friendliness. In OOP, the related data and

functions of an object are placed together within one unit [6]. The design of the whole system could be modeled at a higher level. Any potential problems with the design can be fixed at this level without having to start any programming.

The component approach was used for developing of appropriate software. The applications were subdivided on the small parts or components. These components unified in a whole application during software running. Each component can be modernized independently. It allows modernizing whole application in accordance to further developing conditions. The problem of usage of previously developed software solves with COM model [7-9]. The component developed under COM standard can be used together with any other components. In addition COM allows encapsulating one component into another and provides interface between component and client and realizes all necessary key function [8].

For developing of a whole framework we used distributed programming teams. Such approach [8-9] is well known as outsourcing allowed developing rather complicated software during comparatively short time. We used some methods of management of software development recommended by the company Rational Software and well known as Rational Unified Process (RUP) [11]. For software development the following iteration stages were used:

Developing of technical conditions,

Analysis and design,

Realization,

Quality control and testing,

Configuration control

The paper could be the basis for the project proposal intends to develop and create the control networking infrastructure for the smart grid which enables intelligent distributed control applications and devices that deliver maximum reliability, survivability and responsiveness. Developed system enables any device, speaking any protocol, connected over any network to be integrated into local decision making and connected securely to enterprise IT systems through any IP network. The system helps utilities compete more effectively, reduce operating costs, provide expanded services and help energy users manage and reduce overall energy use.

Each home may have one or more Smart Home Hardware Devices (SHHD) providing useful information from a smart grid perspective. Examples of such devices are sensors (e.g., smart meters), smart appliances (e.g., laundry machine,

dish washer), generators (e.g., PV panels, micro wind turbines, etc.). Electric Vehicles (EV) may also be connected to the EDN, for example during the night for recharging. In our project, we will consider each EV as a sort of smart appliance and thus as a SHHD. Considering distributed generation (not necessarily from home) is very important from a DNO perspective. This motivates their consideration in this project. Smart Home Software Services (SHSS) have the goal of supporting home residents to save on energy costs.

To this end SHSSs will interface, among other things, also with SHHDs. Unfortunately, SHHDs lack a standard interface towards SHHDs. As a result, SHSS cannot be reused across different SHHD vendors since each SHHD has its own (often proprietary) interface.

To some extent, this is like if whenever we write a program we had to worry about the kind of hard disk we are using, the kind of keyboard, etc. Fortunately, this is not the case and instead for each physical device we have a device driver offering to the operating system a uniform, vendor independent abstract interface towards such a device (e.g., hard drive, webcam, etc).

This state of affairs is indeed an obstacle in developing a market for residential home energy services. In fact, in such a situation a SHSS cannot be reused across different SHHD vendors. This limits the market for SHSSs. On the other hand, a SHHD can only be used with the SHSS designed for it. This limits the appeal of installing SHHDs in the first place.

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